

Factors responsible for intrinsic radioprotection

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Intrinsic radioprotection is offered by almost all types of biomolecules, though its degree varies. The different factors which influence it are : types of radiation; dose and dose rate; dose reduction factor; concentration of radioprotector; radioprotective factor; pH, ionic strength, solvent and temperature; oxic, hypoxic and anoxic condition; radiosensitivity of radioprotectors; distance between functional groups and bond energy; radius of gyration and biomolecular configuration; surface area and dose of inactivation; configuration of backbone and supercoiling biomolecules; packing and condensation of biomolecules etc. The present review elucidates their role in intrinsic radioprotection.

Radioprotection has been so far subdivided into three classes i.e. physical, chemical and biological. Intrinsic radioprotection is a relatively new addition in this area of research. All the biomolecules that are responsible for chemical and biological radioprotection contains two portions – active and relatively inactive portions in terms of radioprotective efficacy. An attempt has been made to substantiate the factors that are thought to be responsible for intrinsic radioprotection by giving important literature support and our own data.

Definition :

$$\text{Intrinsic radioprotection} = \frac{\text{Radioprotection offered by the effective constituents of a biomolecule for a defined biological endpoint for an effective dose}}{\text{Radioprotection offered by the actual biomolecule for the same biological endpoint for an effective dose}}$$

Here a biomolecule can be an amino-acid, an aminothiols, an alcohol, a polysaccharide, a protein, an enzyme, a metalloprotein, a glycoprotein, a lipoprotein and a nucleoprotein etc. Defined biological endpoint can be decarboxylation, deamination and desulphuration from compounds containing carboxylic, amino and thiol groups respectively. Dissociation of proteins from nucleoprotein, lipids from lipoproteins, saccharides from glycoproteins, metals from metalloproteins and inactivation of enzymes. This occurs as a result of absorption of ionizing radiation by different

types of compounds mentioned. Effective dose is that absorbed dose that causes dissociation in the simple and complex biomolecules in its two constituent parts – one is responsible for radioprotection and another remains inert.

The different radiochemical and radiobiological factors responsible for intrinsic radioprotection are being explained now as follows :

Radioprotective factor : Radioprotection offered by different compounds are by radical scavenging. The different functional groups, open or potential, interact with the free radicals (e.g. $^{\circ}\text{H}$, $^{\circ}\text{OH}$, $^{\circ}\text{HO}_2$, $-e_{\text{aq}}$) in aqueous solution thereby nullifying their derangement capacity of biomacromolecules present in cells. The summation of the atomic weights of these functional groups divided by molecular weight of the compound has been denoted as radioprotective factor.

Dose rate and dose : For a fixed total dose the functional groups responsible for radioprotection get depleted from a radioprotector depending upon dose rate. 5-Hydroxy-L-tryptophan and L-cysteine are examples of it¹. This is true for biomolecules also. DNA², nucleohistone², nucleoprotamine³ etc. when are subjected to gamma radiation under different dose rates deplete the constituent histones and protamines, pentose sugars etc. to different extents. Hence the intrinsic radioprotective efficacy as offered by these moieties varies. Hence intrinsic radioprotection is dependent upon dose rate. It holds good for H₃-DNA⁴ and H₄-DNA⁵ also. For nucleohistone when dose rate increased by a factor of 190 depletion of pentose sugar was by a factor of 4 and that of protein depletion was by a factor of 2.5 for a concentration of 100 µg/ml. Intrinsic protection of-

Table 1. Effect of gamma irradiation on DNA, protamine, nucleoprotamine, nucleohistone, reconstituted H₃-DNA and H₄-DNA complexes

DNA Protamine DNP				Nucleohistone			H ₃ -DNA complex (25 : 25 µg/ml)		H ₄ -DNA complex (25 : 25 µg/ml)		
Concn. 30 µg/ml				Concn. 100 µg/ml			Solvent 0.15 M		Solvent 0.9%		
Solvent 0.9%				Solvent 0.9%			SSC buffer		sodium chloride		
Sodium chloride				Dose 100 Gy			Dose rate 0.0136 Gy/s				
Dose rate 2.25 Gy/s											
Dose (Gy)	%H	%H	%H	Dose rate (Gy/s)	Pentose sugar (µg/ml)	Histone (µg/ml)	Dose (Gy)	H ₃ unirr./irr.	Dose (Gy)	Dose rate (Gy/s) 0.0106 2.15	
1	1	3	7.7	0.0156	1.50	18.0	5	0.004	20	10.6	28.5
10	6.8	14.5	11.0	2.92	6.00	45.0	10	0.016	30	12.0	41.3
100	13	25	14.5				15	0.072	40	14.7	48.0
							20	0.160	50	17.3	52.0
							25	0.160			
							50	0.240			

Here, %H = percentage hyperchromicity; H₃ unirr./irr. = H₃ histone depleted from H₃-DNA complex in the unirradiated state compared to the irradiated state at a particular dose.

ferred by H₃ histone to DNA decreases with dose for a dose rate of 0.0136 Gy/s. For H₄-DNA complex when dose rate is varied by ~200 times, variation in hyperchromicity changed from 17.3% to 52% (Table 1).

pH, ionic strength, temperature and solvent :

Chemical radioprotectors contain ionisable functional groups (e.g. -SH, -NH₂, -COOH, pyrrole etc.). So ionization of radioprotectors is influenced by pH. For biological radioprotectors unfolding of tertiary structure is also pH dependent. Ionic strength influences the ionic environment of the radioprotectors. This alters the effect of ionizing radiation – induced free radicals to interact with radioprotectors. While at a higher temperature the diffusion of free radicals and metabolic processes will be enhanced, at a lower temperature these will be slower. Low temperature will allow better and efficient repair of radiation damage^{6,7}. The stabilization of protein structures by high concentrations of inert co-solutes has frequently been analysed in terms of preferential solvent occupancy of the protein domain at the expense of small amount of co-solutes. The solvation parameters thus represent a measure of the difference between the apparent volume in the protein region that is inaccessible to co-solute and the corresponding volume that is also inaccessible to solvent⁸.

Type of radiation :

Ionising radiation-induced damage to biomacromolecules, cells and tissues are controlled by type of radiation. These can be particulate (e.g. electrons, positrons, pro-

tons, neutrons, α-particles, etc.) or electromagnetic (e.g. gamma rays, X-rays etc.). Linear energy transfer or LET is a measure of the amount of energy released per micron of track of any ionizing radiation. This gives an indication of biological disruption expected. Biological damage is greater for high LET than for low LET. For quantitation of biological effect relative biological effectiveness (RBE) is used. This is a ratio of biological disruption from the radiation to that from 250 kVp X-rays.

Dose reduction factor (DRF)^{9,10} :

The magnitude of chemical protection against radiation damage is most commonly assessed by dose reduction factor for the radioprotector.

Dose reduction factor (DRF) =

$$\frac{LD_{50}(30) \text{ for protected animals}}{LD_{50}(30) \text{ for unprotected animals}} = D_1/D_0$$

where D₁ = dose for protected animals and D₀ = dose for unprotected animals.

Concentration and DRF¹¹ :

The relationship between concentration and dose reduction factor is given by :

$$F = \frac{M(C_{Rp}) + k}{(C_{Rp}) + k}$$

where (C_{Rp}) is the concentration of radioprotector.

m = maximum value of F i.e. when $(C_{Rp}) = \infty$; K = value of (C_{Rp}) when $F = m + 1/2$.

*Oxic, hypoxic and anoxic condition*¹²⁻¹⁴ :

Degree of oxygenation during irradiation determines radiosensitivity of radioprotectors as well as cells and tissues. Concentration of hydroxyl and hydroperoxy radicals are dependent upon partial pressure of oxygen. A drug or a radioprotector which decreases the extent of oxygenation should exhibit a better radioprotective effect compared to fully oxygenated solution. Under different status of oxygenation oxy-heamoglobin concentration will also vary. Hence tissue oxygenation will also vary, thereby influencing radioprotective efficacy. The chemical and biochemical catalysts for these processes are heamin, cytochromes and other metalloproteins. Mostly thiol compounds have been used for radioprotection under anoxic, hypoxic or oxic conditions.

*Radiosensitivity*¹⁵ :

It has been found that there is almost a reverse relationship between radiosensitivity and radioprotective efficacy. Radiosensitivity decreased in the following order : 5HI2AA

> 5HI3AA > 5HI > 5HT > 5HTP. But radioprotective efficacy decreased in the following order : 5HTP > 5HT > 5HI3AA > 5HI2AA > 5HI.

*Distance between functional groups and bond energy*¹⁶ :

For aminothioli radioprotectors a general rule has emerged that the necessary requirements for radioprotective activity are : a two or three carbon backbone separating a thiol or two potential thiols and a primary or secondary amino functional group as given by : $R-NH-C_2-C_1-SR'$.

The optimal size of the carbon chain separating the amino- and thiol functional groups is made of two carbons. Separating these by more than 3-carbons abolishes radioprotective activity. The bond energy by which the functional groups are attached with the main chain determines at what dose these will be cleaved. After cleaving the rest part of the molecule is incapable of giving radioprotection. This has been reported for L-cysteine, cystamine and 5-hydroxy-L-tryptophan¹.

Table 2 gives a few important radioprotectors with some physico-chemical and radiobiological parameters.

Table 2. Chemical radioprotectors with some physicochemical and radiobiological parameters

Radio-protector	Functional groups	Radio-protective factor	DRF	Biological end point	Dose and dose rate	Type of radiation	Ref.
5HTP	-NH ₂ , -COOH, -OH, indole	0.422	1.20	Survival	10.5 Gy 6.9-8.6 Gy/min	Co-60 gamma	17
5HT	-NH ₂ , OH, indole	0.272	1.30	Survival			18
Cysteine	-NH ₂ , -SH, -COOH	0.776	1.7	Survival	8 Gy 0.0035 Gy/s	X-rays	19
Cystine	-CO ₂ H, NH ₂	0.508	1.3	Enzyme inactivation		X-rays	20
Cystamine	-NH ₂	0.21	1.7				21
Cysteamine	-NH ₂ , -SH	0.635	1.7	Chinese hamster V79 cells	170 Ke V/ μ m	X-rays	22
AET	-NH ₂ , =NH, -SH	0.683	2.1	Mouse bone marrow cells	0.008-0.048 Gy/s	Co-60 gamma	23
MPG	-SH, -CONH	0.465	1.4	Mouse liver body weight ³ H water	5 μ Ci/gm	β -radiation	24
WR 2721	-NH ₂ , -NH, -SH	0.313	2.15	Survival	0.033 Gy/s	Co-60 gamma	25

5HTP = 5-Hydroxy-L-tryptophan; 5HT = 5-hydroxytryptamine; AET = β -aminoethylisothiuronium bromide hydrobromide; MPG = β -mercaptopyonylglycine.

*Radius of gyration and biomolecular conformation*²⁶ :

It has been reported that radius of gyration increased with unfolding of α -lactalbumin, the R_g values in the native, molten globule and denatured states being 1.37, 1.54 and 2.83 nm. The susceptibility to radiation-induced damage is more for unfolded biopolymer. With increase in R_g radioprotective efficacy is expected to decrease.

*Surface area and dose of inactivation*²⁷ :

Accessible surface area of proteins is connected with D_{37} in an inverse manner. Here D_{37} = characteristic dose of inactivation = dose necessary to decrease intact protein band intensity to 37% of original. The dose dependent decay of enzyme activity, A , was fitted by

$$A_D/A_0 = e^{(-D/D_{37})} = e^{-kD}$$

where A_0 and A_D are the activity of enzyme in the native and irradiated state at dose D . This has been found with catalase, ovalbumin, transferrin, carbonic anhydrase and trypsin inhibitor. For all these biopolymers with decrease in surface area D_{37} have increased. The surface areas of the biopolymers are 7.5, 6.1, 3.5, 2.3 and 2.2 (nm²) and their corresponding D_{37} values are 8.2, 11.7, 28.5, 47.7 and 86.7 (Mrad) respectively.

*Configuration of backbone and supercoiling biomolecules*²⁸⁻³² :

Among the supercoiling biomolecules proteins and enzymes are being mentioned here. Some of these enzymes are nitrate reductase, aspartate transcarbamylase, carbonic anhydrase, β -galactosidase and catalase. It is known that these enzymes offer radioprotection. For these enzymes when these are exposed to radiation breaks are not produced at random along the backbone peptide chain but at defined sites. If these sites are the bonds joining the functional groups with the rest of the molecules that will definitely affect the efficacy of intrinsic radioprotection. LET of radiation, total dose, dose rate, solvent accessible surface area are the determining factors.

*Packing and intrinsic radioprotection*³³⁻³⁵ :

Compaction induces rigidity to radiation-induced cleavage of functional moieties present in DNA, nucleohistone (native and reconstituted), nucleoprotamine (native and reconstituted), lipoproteins, glycoproteins and polysaccharides etc. Hence the degree of radioprotection is directly proportional to degradation.

The packing of DNA and its compaction in stepwise fashion up to chromosome has been shown. Moreover, the compaction of DNA in *E. coli*, sperm head and humans chromosome has been included (Table 3). Nucleohistone –

Table 3. Dimension of chromosome obtained from different sources³³, compaction steps for chromosome³⁴ and different fractions of histone^{35,36}.

Dimension (μm)	Length (mm)		Condensation (DNA length/dimension)
	A°	Single step	
<i>E. coli</i> chromosome	2.5	1.35	675
Human chromosome	6.5	34	5000
Sperm head	10	500	50000
Nucleosome	100	7	7
Solenoid	300 \times 100	6	40
Supersolenoid	4000	40	1600
Chromosome	10000	5	8000
Histones*	Mol. end to end distance		Compact
	wt.	(A°)	volume (A°) ³
H ₁	21500	720	10395
H _{2A}	14004	530	109035
H _{2B}	13774	555	187128
H ₃	15324	1056	213135
H ₄	11282	874	117374
H ₅	14225	400	37619

*Obtained from chicken.

a constituent of chromosome is constituted of different fractions of histones. These histones also have got compaction. The molecular weights, end to end distance and compaction of these are also included. As these histones are bound with DNA their compaction increases. The packing ratio of all types of reconstituted nucleohistone is possible to be found out. The protection offered by different fractions of histones to DNA increases with compaction.

Conclusion : So, not only radiobiological properties of radioprotectors but also their configurational aspects in unirradiated and differently irradiated states in solution play important roles in determining the intrinsic radioprotection.

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